

APPLYING THE BLOCK MODEL APPROACH IN TEACHING GRADE III MATHEMATICS IN STA. CRUZ ELEMENTARY SCHOOL

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Applying the Block Model Approach in Teaching Grade III Mathematics in Sta. Cruz Elementary School

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Abstract

The primary aim of this research is to find out if block model approach could help in enhancing the academic performance among the Grade III pupils of Santa Cruz Elementary School, District I-A, Schools Division of Antipolo City school year 2023 – 2024. Specifically, this study aimed to determine the performance of the Grade III pupils in Mathematics during the pre-test and post-test. It also sought to find answer if there is a significant difference in the performance of the respondents after utilizing block model approach in teaching Mathematics lessons. The quasi-experimental pre-test and post-test design was utilized in the study. There were forty-one (41) pupils who were subjected as the respondents in the action research. Teacher-made pre-test and post-test in Mathematics were the tools utilized to gather the needed data. These questionnaires were validated by the master teacher in-charge of testing the principal approved for its used. In order to answer the specific problems posted in the study, the researcher utilized the mean and the t-test. Based on the results found, the respondents portrayed low performance in their Mathematics class as reflected on their scores during the pre-test while they showed enhanced academic performance in the said subject after integrating the block model approach in teaching which resulted on improved post-test scores. Furthermore, results of the study revealed a significant difference from pre-test to post-test.

Keywords: *block model approach, performance of grade III pupils in mathematics*

Introduction

The low results of the diagnostic test taken in her class served as the baseline data that the researcher took into accounts while undertaking this research study. The diagnostic test was administered to identify the learners' areas of strength as well as their areas of weakness. Given the exam data the researcher had gathered from her class, she posed the question of what she might do to help her class perform better. The intervention she will use to teach the subject for eight (8) weeks is the block model approach. With the hopes that using the aforementioned intervention will improve learners' performance in the subject for the school year 2023 – 2024.

Mathematics is one of several academic subjects that are taught in schools and are important to education. It is one of the academic fields that contributes to the development of technology and science. Mathematics is important for problem solving in all fields, from the simple to the complex, from the abstract to the concrete. For most kids, learning mathematics is not fun since it requires specific knowledge and critical thinking. Students' perceptions of mathematics are not in line with reality, despite the fact that they typically view it as a difficult, uninteresting, frightening, and oftentimes frustrating subject that creates learning difficulties. These pupils' perceptions lead to less satisfying learning outcomes. Apart from that, the fact of what actually occurred in the field shows that there aren't many engaging educational materials available to promote mathematics study. Most educational resources that are available are in the form of textbooks, and traditional learning paradigms are often used by instructors to teach content.

Due to the constantly evolving nature of the Philippine K–12 educational system, educators must be flexible, creative, and inventive in order to help students develop into critical thinkers and competent problem solvers (Casinillo & Aure, 2018). The secret to helping students improve their problem-solving abilities is a math teacher's teaching tactics (Leonard, 2018). To help students effectively apply concepts into the solution process, it is required to model a procedure for visualizing problem information (Kaur, 2019). This gives rise to the idea of Block Modeling. According to this study, explicit education in the usage of Block Models as a visual way to solving mathematical issues helps students become more adept at solving difficulties.

One of the most important aspects of learning mathematics is developing effective problem-solving techniques, and teachers place a high priority on this. Frequently, the first step in assisting pupils in comprehending an issue and coming up with a solution is to visualize it (Kenan, 2018). The Block Model approach became well-liked in Singapore because it gives students the ability to solve math problems that were previously limited to advanced students. When representing simple and multi-step word problems, students are taught to draw bars to show the relationships between the problem's known aspects and to place one or more question marks to indicate what more they need to research. Positive experiences learning to solve mathematical puzzles appear to correlate well with high academic accomplishment (Casinillo & Casinillo, 2020; Casinillo et al., 2020a).

Students can acquire the concrete experiences that are necessary to comprehend and manipulate the abstract symbols of mathematics with the use of mathematical models. There are numerous opportunities to apply heuristics like "Use a model," "Draw a diagram," or "Use visualization" while using the model technique. In mathematics, visual representation is the process of building models that represent mathematical data. It is a crucial ability since more advanced math and scientific classes depend more and more on problem-solving techniques including spatial reasoning and visualization (Zhang, Ding, Stegall, & Mo, 2012). Block modeling helps students of all ages develop their algebraic thinking skills and helps them to give concrete answers to abstract situations (Petti, 2014).

In the subjects of science and mathematics, Filipino pupils have significantly underperformed on national achievement tests (NAT) (Suarez & Casinillo, 2020). Filipino students may perform at a lower level than the majority of students from other countries, particularly when it comes to problem-solving.

When there is no visible solution, issue solving is the cognitive processing done to achieve a goal. Stendall (2019) asserts that learning skills and problem-solving depend heavily on one's capacity for strong focus, meaningful perception, logical thought, and efficient memory utilization. Students' talents differ in these areas. Cognitive and psychological variables may have an impact on one's capacity to apply mathematical knowledge and reasoning to solve problems. According to Miranda (2016), youngsters who have trouble paying attention, describing the orientation of shape and space, making visual and aural perceptions, memorization of simple objects, and language comprehension may have trouble thinking and learning.

De Guzman (2012) examined the Block Model Approach in Problem Solving: Impact on Grade V Mathematics Students' Problem Solving Performance. The outcome demonstrates that teaching mathematics requires problem-solving abilities, which students find challenging because the word problems are misrepresented. Students frequently represent the words "more than" as addition and "less than" as difference. The concrete-representation-abstract paradigm of teaching mathematics is the foundation of the block model technique. According to a groundbreaking new study by Joonkoo Park and Elizabeth Brannon (2013), learning is most effective when it happens when different parts of the brain are used. Students use a different part of the brain when working with symbols like numbers than when working with visual and spatial information like a set of dots. The researchers discovered that when the two brain regions were interacting, mathematics learning and performance were maximized (Park & Brannon, 2013). Each of these illustrations draws attention to the mathematics involved in the problem and aids in the students' development of multiplication comprehension. Students' knowledge of mathematical concepts is aided by pictures. Additionally, visual mathematics helps individuals recognize the creativity in mathematics and promotes higher order thinking as well as communication.

Mahoney (2012) studied the effects of Singapore's Model Method, also called "model drawing" or "bar modelling," on the word problem-solving skills of third- and fourth-graders. Over the course of eight teaching sessions, a kid in the third grade received the researcher-designed teaching intervention using a single-case design. The percentage of problems performed correctly was the dependent variable, and it was measured repeatedly during the experiment's three phases (baseline, intervention, and maintenance) using evaluation probes that the researcher had created.

A research by Jonathan Hsu (2013) examined the benefits and drawbacks of using Singapore math methods with high school pupils in a private school geometry lesson. The data from surveys and interviews was gathered using a qualitative approach inside a constructivism paradigm. After completing a word problem exercise, the students were given an introduction to Singapore math's bar modeling methods. The pupils were ecstatic about Singapore Math's bar modeling methods and were clearly pleased. His approach of teaching, which engages all of the kids visually, is influenced by Singapore math. I'll be using his visually-oriented teaching approach all the time to get my kids interested in arithmetic. High schools ought to implement Singapore Math's bar modeling strategies, since they have the potential to boost students' self-assurance in mathematics while also enhancing their critical thinking and problem-solving abilities.

Students can effectively organize their thoughts, gain a solid understanding of the word problem's components, and gain a deeper understanding of word problems by applying the Block Model to their word problem solution. Furthermore, encouraging students to thoroughly research the questions and the connections between the data in the problem aids in their ability to analyze the issue and come up with a reasoned answer. By using this strategy, students are solving for the missing variable and applying algebraic thinking to their problem solving. Even the most difficult issues, nevertheless, become easier to understand because to this clever way of using a symbolic bar to express numerical values and connections.

A study was conducted by Morina and Vondrova (2021) entitled "Block Model Approach and Its Effect on Word Problem Solving, A Case Study" showed that even a short introduction to the block model approach enabled the pupils to connect successfully the verbal, visual, and symbolic representations of the word problem. Word problem solving is an important part of school mathematics, yet pupils often fail in it. In this case study, we investigated whether an introduction of the block model approach would help two 4th grade pupils in Kosovo to solve word problems. The study follows the observational methodology as it allows to gather 'live' data from naturally occurring social contexts (Cohen et al., 2007). As our main aim was to get an insight into the pupils' appropriation of the block model method, a qualitative method of a case study (Cohen, Manion & Morrison, 2007) and task-based think-aloud interviews (Maher & Sigley, 2014) was used. Think-aloud interviews were conducted, and their transcripts were analyzed in a qualitative way. This is an encouraging result showing that the block model approach can be introduced more widely.

Another, the study by Jorigue (2019) entitled "Teaching Percent to Grade 6 - Matulungin Pupils Using Block Model Approach" revealed that the pupils learned the concept of percent and its application using the Block Model Approach better and they have positive feedback in using the method in understanding and applying the concept they learned in the lesson. In the diagnostic test conducted last June 2017, the Grade Six pupils got a mean score of 22.72 with an MPS of 45.44%. One of the least learned skills is about percent. Even though there are various teaching strategies and problem-solving approaches that engages pupils to participate in Mathematics Class, they still spend more time in solving using the usual algorithm. This Action Research explored the use of block model approach in understanding percent to 40 pupils of Grade VI -Matulungin for School Year 2017 -2018. A pre-test was administered to determine

the prior knowledge of the pupils on percent. For this unit, lessons were prepared using the Block Model Approach and the mastery level was determined to measure if the target was achieved. It ran for three (3) weeks and after the unit, a post-test was administered to the class. The result of the daily assessment of the daily lessons for the duration of the study were taken and its Mean-Percentage Scores (MPS) ranges from 74.67 to 77.58 with an average MPS of 75.72% and at least 20 out of 39 pupils who reached 80% Mastery Level. The topic "Finding the Percentage" gained the highest MPS of 77.58%. On the other hand, the topic "Percentage as Fractions and Decimals (Day 1) obtained the lowest MPS of 74.67% because of the 2-day class suspension due to Typhoon Maring. The Pre-Test has an MPS of 34.67% and the Post-Test got an MPS of 75.13% with an increment of 40.46%. It is recommended to all Mathematics Teachers to use the Block Model Approach in teaching the concepts of Mathematics from Grade 1 to Grade 6. Conduct a Learning Action Cell on the use of Block Model Approach to all teachers.

Also, the study conducted by Garzon and Casinillo (2021) entitled "Visualizing Mathematics: The Use of Block Models for Strategic Problem Solving" stated that utilization of block models gives high potential in developing strategic problem-solving ability of learners. The ability to visually manipulate problem quantities is often the key to understand effectively the concept towards proper solution process. Modeling blocks in a problem text is a visual mathematical technique that utilizes bar models to express relationship between known and unknown numerical elements. Facing a dismal performance among students entering high school with poor basic problem-solving skills, this study is an attempt to investigate how block model approach potentially reinforce students' heuristic skills (analytical & procedural) in solving mathematical problems. Two classes of grade 7 students in Ibarra National High School, Maasin City, Philippines were used as participants which is assigned into groups, that is, control and experimental groups. Control group was taught using conventional method while the experimental group was taught using the concept of block model. Using quasi-experimental design, the data analysis revealed significant increase in scores and significant mean difference in problem-solving skills between groups who used and did not use block model. This approach should be incorporated by mathematics teachers in their teaching strategies.

Furthermore, the study by Lucasia (2020) entitled "Applying the Block Model Approach in Teaching Mathematics in the Philippine Classroom" concluded that drawing a bar to make a model assists Grade seven students to solve word problems. The teaching of Mathematics involves problem solving skills in which proved to be difficult on the part of the students due to misrepresentation of the word problems. This problem is associated to the low performance in Mathematics of Filipino students both in local and international assessments. This paper addresses the problem-solving skills of Filipino Grade Seven students employing the Block Model Approach which is based on concrete - representation – abstract principle of teaching Mathematics. In this quasi-experimental study, two Grade Seven sections participated in a three-week trial of the method. Comparing pretest and posttest scores showed both groups, Non-Block Model Approach and Block Model Approach groups gained an improved performance in Mathematics. The test of significance showed that the Block Model Approach provides better results. In addition, the learning gain of the experimental group under the Block Model group was higher than the mean learning gain of the control group. It is recommended for the public basic education teachers to consider the Block Model in their lessons to improve the mathematical ability of the Filipino learners.

Moreover, the study conducted by Downie et al. (2023) entitled "The Importance of Developing a Metric to Classify Student Experience in Mathematics within the Framework of Intensive Block Teaching" showed both reliability and robustness in being able to identify students likely to have difficulty in studying undergraduate mathematics especially within the context of the time limited intensive block teaching, permitting early intervention to help students at risk of failure to succeed. The number of students enrolling in higher level mathematics units at high school have been in decline for a number of years. This is of particular concern when they then continue their studies within undergraduate STEM disciplines at University, leading academics to search for better methods to support mathematical instruction. The aim of this study was to investigate the development of a simple and robust tool to classify students' mathematical capacity within a time compressed block teaching environment. One hundred and seventy-six first year students completed a survey reflecting on their level of comfort, competence, and enjoyment of mathematics, including their highest level of previous study in the discipline. Students also completed a short quiz to establish a pre-learning numeracy skill baseline. The survey provided data for development of the metric, from which, three groups ranked on their mathematical ability (low, medium and high) were identified which were then matched with scores arising from their baseline assessment. The classification grouping was uniform across all four offerings of the mathematics unit taught and matched with common baseline assessment scores.

Lastly, by Laurenio and Ventura (2021) entitled "Indigenized Block Modeling Approach in Teaching Mathematics among Iped Intermediate Pupils: Basis for Proposed Instructional Material Development in Mathematics Problem" stated that the use of block models has a great potential for enhancing learners' strategic problem-solving abilities. This study determined the effectiveness of Block Modelling Approach in teaching Mathematics among intermediate Indigenous People Education pupils in LupangPangako Resettlement School, Division of Zambales during the SY 2018-2019 as basis for proposed instructional material development in solving Mathematics problem. The study utilized the descriptive survey research method and descriptive statistics (percentage, frequency counts, and mean), Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and inferential statistics (T - Test) using SPSS version 20. The respondents of the study were the intermediate IPED pupils of LupangPangako Resettlement School with 70 pupils as respondents from Grade IV-Talisay with 25 pupils respondent which focus on four fundamental operation and fraction, Grade V-Kawayan with 25 pupils respondent which focus on four fundamental operation, fraction, decimal, ratio, and percentage and Grade VI-Agocho with 20 pupils respondent which focus on four fundamental operation, fraction, decimals, ratio and proportion, and percentage. As a result,

teachers should include this method into their teaching practices and utilize it as the foundation for developing instructional resources in teaching Mathematics.

The researcher, a mathematics teacher, chose the usage of block model approach as an intervention approach used in her class to help her learners acquire mathematical concepts with enjoyment. Based on the literature studies regarding block model approach mentioned above have proven the effectivity of the intervention in improving the performance of the learners. Hence, the researcher was very positive that this intervention will work in her class to perform better.

Research Questions

The main objective of this action research was to evaluate the effectiveness of Block Model Approach in improving the Performance of Grade III Pupils in Mathematics of Santa Cruz Elementary School, District I-A, City Schools Division of Antipolo City for school year 2023 – 2024. Specifically, the research aimed to find out the answer on the following problems:

1. What is the performance of the Grade III Pupils in Mathematics during the pre-test and post-test?
2. Is there a significant difference in the performance of the Grade III pupils after Block Model Approach was employed?

Methodology

Research Design

In this study, the quasi-experiment design was utilized. According to Rogers (2019) quasi-experimental research designs examine whether there is a causal relationship between independent and dependent variables. Simply defined, the independent variable is the variable of influence and the dependent variable is the variable that is being influenced. In other words, the independent variable is expected to bring about some variation or change in the dependent variable.

In addition, Quasi-experiments are most likely to be conducted in field settings in which random assignment is difficult or impossible. They are often conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of a treatment—perhaps a type of psychotherapy or an educational intervention. There are many different kinds of quasi-experiments, but we will discuss just a few of the most common ones here (Chiang, et. al. 2020).

Furthermore, Cook, et. al (2018), stated that quasi-experimental research is research that resembles experimental research but is not true experimental research. Although the independent variable is manipulated, participants are not randomly assigned to conditions or orders of conditions. Because the independent variable is manipulated before the dependent variable is measured, quasi-experimental research eliminates the directionality problem. But because participants are not randomly assigned—making it likely that there are other differences between conditions—quasi-experimental research does not eliminate the problem of confounding variables. In terms of internal validity, therefore, quasi-experiments are generally somewhere between correlational studies and true experiments.

Samples of forty-one (41) Grade III pupils were used for the experiment. Any pupil belonging to the Grade III class of Santa Cruz Elementary School was automatically a subject for the experiment. The design can provide valid results for the ongoing study, hence, it was utilized.

Sources of Data

The subjects of this action research were the Grade III pupils of Santa Cruz Elementary School located in District I-A, City Schools Division of Antipolo from school year 2023 – 2024. The school was categorized as mega large school with thirty-six (36) sections in each grade level.

Under the researcher's advisory, 41 students were included in the study. They were all study participants, and the learners in this group were heterogenous class. Since the researcher was advising these learners, it was best for her to be the study's respondents so that she could monitor from time to time and check directly on the students' performance.

Instrument and Data Collection

The main instruments used in the study were the questionnaires prepared by the researcher intended for pre-test and post-test. The said tests composed of 40 items each. The number of test items given to the respondents was the standard number of test items in the grade. These were based on the competencies studied for eight (8) weeks and implemented in the class through the use of block model approach in teaching the lessons. The pre-test administered on November 15, 2023 and the post-test was conducted on February 7, 2024. The said questionnaires were also validated by the Master Teacher in-charge in testing and approved by the school principal for its implementation.

Pre-test and post-test were made to evaluate the comparison of the pupils' scores before and after the implementation of the intervention. The researcher also kept a class record with the purpose of recording the performances in Mathematics made by the pupils during the course of research. Results of the test was tabulated, analyzed and interpreted in order to answer the problems posted in the study.

According to Kelly (2019), Pretest can be used diagnostically to determine if there are any gaps in understanding from previous units

taught. Most pretests use elements of review and new material to get a comprehensive picture of student knowledge within a given area. They can be used in this way to assess whether students have retained knowledge from prior lessons.

In addition, according to Berry (2018), pre-test can be used at beginning of a course to establish a subject knowledge baseline and then related to an end of the course exam to look at knowledge added. Pre-tests can also be used as a way to judge the depth of understanding of prerequisite material. Although counter-intuitive, the pre-tests are covering material that the instructor has not covered and that the student is not expected to know. The idea behind the pre-tests is to give the students an indication of material that will be covered and the depth of knowledge required, thus it serves a 'road map' for the topics. In addition, the instructor gets a quantifiable measure of the knowledge that students already possess for a particular topic.

While Post-tests are designed to make a measurement of immediate change, but should or through feedback also serve to drive a learner to reflect on the content they have consumed and to revisit areas of the content where they still have deficiencies. Results from a Post-test are typically compared to results from the same questions administered immediately before an educational intervention. This allows for a more meaningful paired analysis (as cited by Alfonso, 2018). While Posttest provides summative data to teachers and students and ensures students start on the next unit together. Through the posttest, students and teachers can reflect on each student's mastery from the unit, informing future learning activities to ensure student mastery (as cited by Ortiz, 2019). The pre-test and post-test statistical tools were used in the study to determine whether or not the respondents' performance improved.

Data Analysis

The data gathered was statistically treated using mean whereas t-test at 0.05 level of significance was employed to test the difference of the two (2) tests. Data were gathered and analyzed before and after the implementation of the intervention in the subject of the samples for eight (8) weeks. Examination scores were used to measure learners' learning outcomes. Through which results of the pre-test and post-test were compared to note the difference between the scores.

Statement of the problem number 1 utilized the mean statistical tool. According to Manikandan (2016), "mean" is the "average" you're used to, where you add up all the numbers and then divide by the number of numbers. The mean uses all value in the data and hence is an appropriate representation of the data. The mean is then a parameter that measures the central tendency that best resists the fluctuation between different samples. This statistical tool was used to determine the difference between the pretest and posttest examinations. Furthermore, according to Frost (2016), mean measures of central tendency that represents the center point or typical value of a dataset. These measures indicate where most values in a distribution fall and are also referred to as the central location of a distribution. You can think of it as the tendency of data to cluster around a middle value.

T = calculated difference represented in units of standard error. According to Bevans (2020) t-test is a statistical test that is used to compare the means of two groups. It is often used in hypothesis testing to determine whether a process or treatment actually has an effect on the population of interest, or whether two groups are different from one another. A t-test can only be used when comparing the means of two groups.

Furthermore, Hayes (2020) stated that t-test is a type of inferential statistic used to determine if there is a significant difference between the means of two groups, which may be related in certain features. It is mostly used when the data sets, like the data set recorded as the outcome from flipping a coin 100 times, would follow a normal distribution and may have unknown variances. A t-test is used as a hypothesis testing tool, which allows testing of an assumption applicable to a population. The t-test was used because there were two (2) test results being compared in the study.

Results and Discussion

The Performance of the Grade III Pupils in Mathematics During the Pre-test and Post-test

Table 1 shows the Performance of the Grade III Pupils in Mathematics during the Pre-test and Post-test.

It could be noted on Table 1 that the mean scores of the respondents in pretest was 24.17 and during the posttest was 35.88. Results of the pre-test and post-test showed an increase based on the scores of the pupils. Thus, test results showed that during the pre-test, the learners were not able to surpassed the 75% mastery level while during the post-test they surpassed the passing mark. This implied that the intervention used in the study was effective.

Learners obtained lower results in the pre-test due to the reason that they have not studied the contents of the said test. The learners were not yet ready for the competencies being tested. Meanwhile, during the post-test the learners have already acquired the necessary skills and competencies which yielded to satisfactory results of the test being administered. Aside from that, the used of game-based learning approach was considered as the main factor that contributed to higher scores of pupils. One hundred percent of the learners were noted to have scored 32 and above which implied that out of 40-item test the learners mastered the lessons.

The current study findings corroborated with the study findings of Jorigue (2019) which revealed that the pupils learned the concept of percent and its application using the block model approach. A pre-test was administered to determine the prior knowledge of the pupils on percent. For this unit, lessons were prepared using the block model approach and the mastery level was determined to measure if

the target was achieved. It ran for three (3) weeks and after the unit, a post-test was administered to the class. The result of the daily assessment of the daily lessons for the duration of the study were taken and its Mean-Percentage Scores (MPS) ranges from 74.67 to 77.58 with an average MPS of 75.72% and at least 20 out of 39 pupils who reached 80% Mastery Level. Thus, the results of the study revealed that the performance of the learners from pre-test to post-test was improved.

Table 1. *The Performance of the Grade III Pupils in Mathematics during the Pre-test and Post-test*

<i>Pupils</i>	<i>Pre-Test 40 - items</i>	<i>Post-Test 40 - items</i>
1	26	34
2	18	32
3	23	36
4	22	37
5	27	36
6	30	40
7	19	32
8	23	35
9	27	34
10	25	36
11	22	35
12	27	38
13	31	40
14	23	38
15	24	39
16	25	37
17	22	35
18	18	33
19	30	40
20	21	35
21	27	38
22	23	37
23	23	34
24	26	35
25	25	34
26	19	33
27	24	36
28	22	35
29	26	37
30	25	38
31	22	34
32	20	33
33	29	38
34	28	39
35	22	37
36	26	36
37	23	32
38	19	33
39	31	40
40	22	34
41	26	36
Mean	24.17	35.88
MPS	60.425	89.70

Also, the present study findings supported the findings of Garzon and Casinillo (2021) which stated that utilization of block model gives high potential in developing strategic problem-solving ability of learners. The ability to visually manipulate problem quantities is often the key to understand effectively the concept towards proper solution process. Modeling blocks in a problem text is a visual mathematical technique that utilizes bar models to express relationship between known and unknown numerical elements. Using quasi-experimental design, the data analysis revealed significant increase in scores and significant mean difference in problem-solving skills between groups who used and did not use block model. This approach should be incorporated by mathematics teachers in their teaching strategies because it helps improved the performance of the learners.

In addition, the recent study findings corroborated with the Lucasia (2020) applying the block model approach in Teaching Mathematics. This paper addresses the problem-solving skills of Filipino Grade Seven students employing the block model approach which is based on concrete - representation – abstract principle of teaching Mathematics. In this quasi-experimental study, two Grade

Seven sections participated in a three-week trial of the method. Comparing pretest and posttest scores showed both groups, Non-Block Model Approach and Block Model Approach groups gained an improved performance in Mathematics. Thus, the results of the study revealed that using the intervention improved the learners' performance.

Furthermore, the recent study findings corroborated with the findings of Morina and Vondrova (2021) which showed that even a short introduction to the block model approach enabled the pupils to connect successfully the verbal, visual, and symbolic representations of the word problem. Word problem solving is an important part of school mathematics, yet pupils often fail in it. In this case study, we investigated whether an introduction of the block model approach would help two 4th grade pupils in Kosovo to solve word problems. Thus, the results of the study revealed that the performance of the learners were improved.

Test for Significant Difference in the Performance of the Grade III Pupils after Block Model Approach was employed

Figure 2 shows the Test for Significant Difference in the Performance of the Grade III pupils after Block Model was employed.

Figure 2. Test for Significant Difference in the Performance of the Grade III pupils after Block Model Approach was employed

Figure 2 reveals the result of t-test in the analysis of data to either the use of block model approach is effective in the performance of the Grade III Pupils. The means of Pre-Test and Post-Test are significantly different at $p < 0.05$.

The absolute value of the calculated t exceeds the critical value ($-33.10 > 2.02$), so the means are significantly different. Therefore, the hypothesis that there is no significant difference between the results of pre-test and post-test in which the used of block model approach is highly rejected. This implies also that the used of block model approach in the teaching learning process showed a significant difference in the improvement of pupils the performance in Mathematics.

The current study findings corroborated with the study findings of Downie et al. (2023) which showed both reliability and robustness in being able to identify students likely to have difficulty in studying undergraduate mathematics especially within the context of the time limited intensive block teaching, permitting early intervention to help students at risk of failure to succeed. The number of students enrolling in higher level mathematics units at high school have been in decline for a number of years. The survey provided data for development of the metric, from which, three groups ranked on their mathematical ability (low, medium and high) were identified which were then matched with scores arising from their baseline assessment. Thus, results of the study showed that there was a significant difference in the performance of the learners.

Moreover, the latest study findings supported the findings of Laurenio and Ventura (2021) which stated that the use of block models has a great potential for enhancing learners' strategic problem-solving abilities. This study determined the effectiveness of Block Modelling Approach in teaching Mathematics among intermediate pupils during the SY 2018-2019. The study utilized the descriptive survey research method and descriptive statistics (percentage, frequency counts, and mean), Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and inferential statistics (T - Test) using SPSS version 20. As a result, the study's findings revealed that there was a significant difference in the performance of the learners.

Conclusions

The respondents portrayed low performance in their Mathematics class as reflected on their scores during the pre-test while they showed enhanced academic performance in the said subject after integrating the block model approach in teaching which resulted on improved post-test scores. Furthermore, results of the study revealed a significant difference from pre-test to post-test.

Based on the findings and conclusion, the following recommendations are presented;

Teacher should be familiarized in using or adopting block model approach that can be used in teaching mathematical concepts and or skills.

Teacher should motivate pupils to use the block model approach that are related to the learning contents. This will help them learn skills at their own pace.

Learners who has difficulty in learning the content should seek assistance from their peers. They may seek assistance in applying the intervention from those who are more knowledgeable and expert such related activities.

Institution should give ample trainings to those teachers who are not yet familiar in using block model approach in their teaching especially those teachers handling lower grades and lower sections.

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